

Spatial Arithmetic explains Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle and Schrödinger's wave function.

- Spatial Arithmetic explains Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle

In previous articles, I proved that mass (what we call matter) is essentially time (t'), an untransformed spatial value. And the formula: $f/f_0 = t'/t$.

Thus, a change in the distribution of the untransformed spatial value (t'/t) will change the intrinsic frequency of the particle.

To change the distribution of the untransformed spatial value of the particle, we must affect the particle's energy (add or subtract), and then the particle's intrinsic frequency will change.

The energy equation in terms of waves has the form $E = hf$

Ta có $E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{motion}} + E_{\text{rest}}$

$$\Leftrightarrow hf_{\text{total}} = hf_{\text{motion}} + hf_{\text{rest}} \quad \Leftrightarrow f_{\text{total}} = f_{\text{motion}} + f_{\text{rest}}$$

This means that as the particle moves, a portion of the wave (intrinsic frequency) that has not yet been transformed is converted into a moving wave (observable frequency).

In particles with mass, this intrinsic frequency is a spatial value that remains untransformed and therefore unobservable, only measurable through interaction. With photons, however, this frequency is spread out (the spatial value has fully transformed), making it observable (directly measurable).

Thus, a particle with mass is essentially a bundle of energy units with the same distribution of untransformed spatial values. A larger mass means the particle has more energy units. Each energy unit has $t^2 = SV + t'^2$. When the particle receives more energy, it gains more energy units. These energy units will change their spatial value distribution according to $t^2 = SV + t'^2$. The total untransformed spatial value is the mass, and this mass remains constant to ensure the specificity of the particle type. At this point, the untransformed spatial value of each energy unit decreases, so the particle's intrinsic frequency decreases.

The motion of particles is influenced not only by the spatial distribution of the particle's values but also by the spatial interaction of the environment. Particles, which are essentially waves, move in a wave-like manner (internal frequency and frequency of motion), and are further affected by environmental factors, making their motion even more complex.

The uncertainty of particles stems from the fact that they are essentially energy acting in a wave-like manner. Momentum is measured based on the particle's mass (the particle's frequency); when measuring position, we are only at a point on the wave phase, so momentum cannot be measured, and vice versa.

let's consider Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle:

We have:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

Or: $s.m.v \geq \hbar/2$

$\Leftrightarrow s.m.s/t \geq \hbar/2$

$\Leftrightarrow SV.c^2.m/t \geq \hbar/2$

The right side is a constant; let's consider the left side: As proven, mass is the untransformed (mapped) spatial value. Therefore, here we perform the mapping operation $m \rightarrow t'$:

$SV.c^2.m/t$ when mapping we get $SV.c^2.t'/t = SV.c^2.f/f_0$

That means if we can measure the ratio f/f_0 (with $f/f_0 = t'/t$). We can calculate the SV (determine its position).

Thus, there is actually no uncertainty; uncertainty arises when the particle's position cannot be determined because we cannot directly measure the particle's intrinsic frequency or know the wave phase at the time of measurement. Furthermore, because the particle is always subject to spatial interactions with the environment, the particle's equation of motion becomes complex (not the Schrödinger wave function; in fact, the Schrödinger wave function is a general description based on experimental practice and mathematical formulas for probability and wave phase, essentially a probability function).

Under ideal conditions (no spatial value interaction), if we consider a very small space, we can calculate the ratio f/f_0 based on $f/f_0 = t'/t$, knowing the wave phase and measuring momentum, and then we can calculate the velocity and position. However, this is difficult to achieve because ideal conditions are almost impossible, but that doesn't mean the particle is inherently uncertain. The uncertainty is only due to the limitations of the measuring instrument and the complexity of the environment interacting with the particle. This is similar to the three-body problem.

- Spatial arithmetic explains the Schrödinger wave function:

From $f/f_0 = t'/t$ it can be seen that the double-slit experiment is essentially just a change in the frequency of the particle. When a detector is present (with direct energy interaction with the particle), the particle changes its spatial distribution of values, thereby changing its intrinsic frequency as well as its motion frequency, thus changing the resulting outcome.

We have the general equation:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} + V(x)\psi(x) = E\psi(x)$$

When this function is converted and the mapping is performed, we will obtain an expression with $(f/f_0).SV$. This means that the wave function (the probability of a particle appearing at a point) depends on the frequency ratio of the particle and the spatial distribution of values. This means there is no randomness (uncertainty) involved; if we have enough parameters, we can completely calculate the particle's position. The Schrödinger wave function and the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle are essentially the same.

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.